

Studies on the densities, viscosities and adiabatic compressibilities of some mineral salts in aqueous binary mixture of tetrahydrofuran at different temperatures

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The densities, viscosities and ultrasonic velocities of some mineral salts, viz. ammonium nitrate (NH_4NO_3), potassium nitrate (KNO_3), magnesium nitrate ($\text{Mg}(\text{NO}_3)_2$) and calcium nitrate ($\text{Ca}(\text{NO}_3)_2$) in 30 mass % tetrahydrofuran + water mixture have been measured at temperatures 303, 308, 313, 318 and 323 K. Apparent molar volumes (V_ϕ), viscosity B -coefficients and adiabatic compressibility (β) of these electrolytes were derived from these data supplemented with their densities, viscosities and ultrasonic velocities, respectively. The limiting apparent molar volumes (V_ϕ^0) and experimental slopes (S_V^*) obtained from Masson equation have been interpreted in terms of ion-solvent and ion-ion interactions, respectively. The viscosity data have been analyzed using Jones-Dole equation. The results show that these electrolytes have structure-making capacities in this solvent-mixture. The compressibility data also indicate the electrostriction of solvent molecules around the metal ions.

It is well-known that the reaction medium plays an important role in determining reactivity which is reflected in thermodynamic, transport and spectral properties¹. In order to gain insight into the mechanism of such interactions, thermodynamic and transport studies involving one or more solutes in mixed solvent systems are highly useful. Studies on the apparent molar volumes of electrolytes and dependence of viscosity on concentration of solutes and temperature of solutions have been employed as a function of studying ion-ion and ion-solvent interactions². It has been found by a number of workers³ that the addition of electrolyte could break or make the structure of a liquid. Since the viscosity is a property of the liquid which depends upon the intermolecular forces, the structural aspects of the liquid can be inferred from the viscosity of solutions at different concentrations and temperatures.

Tetrahydrofuran, commercially known as collosolves, is a good industrial solvent. It figures prominently in the high energy battery industry and finds application in the organic syntheses as manifested from the physicochemical studies in this medium⁴. In spite of the potential applications of this solvent, there are relatively few solute-solute and solute-solvent interaction studies in this class of solvents. Hence, as a part of a series of investigations⁵⁻⁷ on the classical nature of solutes and their mutual and specific interactions with the solvent molecules, we have performed density, viscosity and ultrasonic velocity measurements in 30 mass % tetrahydrofuran (THF) + water mixture of ammonium nitrate (NH_4NO_3), potassium nitrate (KNO_3), magnesium nitrate ($\text{Mg}(\text{NO}_3)_2$) and calcium nitrate ($\text{Ca}(\text{NO}_3)_2$) as a

function of temperature (303, 308, 313, 318 and 323 K) in order to unravel the nature of various types of interactions prevailing in these electrolyte solutions.

Results and discussion

The experimental values of density (ρ_0) and viscosity (η_0) of pure THF and 30 mass % of THF + H_2O mixtures at 298, 303, 308, 313, 318 and 323 K are reported in Table 1.

Table 1 reveals that the viscosity (η_0) of the solvent mixtures (THF + H_2O) at the investigated temperatures increases rapidly to a maximum at about 40 mass % of THF and thereafter decreases. Such characteristics in the viscosity vs composition curve is a manifestation of strong specific interaction⁸ between unlike molecules predominated by H-bonding interaction.

The apparent molar volume (V_ϕ) of liquid solutions was calculated from the relation,

$$V_\phi = M / \rho_0 - 1000(\rho - \rho_0) / \rho_0 c \quad (1)$$

where c is the molarity of the solution and the other symbols have their usual significance. The correction to V_ϕ due to hydrolysis of electrolytes may be negligible, since the strong hydrogen bonding⁹ between THF and H_2O will reduce the hydrolysis of these electrolytes by free water molecules considerably.

Application of the Redlich-Meyer equation was not possible due to the lack of data on the compressibility and pressure variation of dielectric constant, necessary to calculate the theoretical limiting slope (S_V^*). Thus, the

Table 1. Physical properties of pure tetrahydrofuran (THF) and different mass % of THF + H₂O mixtures of different temperatures

<i>T</i> K	Mass % THF	ρ_0 , g cm ³		η_0 , cP	
		Present work	lit.	Present work	lit.
298	20	0.98668	0.98668 ^a	1.49002	1.49002 ^a
303	20	0.98488	–	1.31155	–
308	20	0.98309	0.98309 ^a	1.13310	1.13310 ^a
313	20	0.98019	–	1.05991	–
318	20	0.97730	0.97730 ^a	0.89670	0.89670 ^a
323	20	0.97631	0.97631 ^a	0.89535	0.89535 ^a
298	30	0.97833	0.97833 ^a	1.67977	1.67977 ^a
303	30	0.97634	–	1.47326	–
308	30	0.97434	0.97434	1.26674	1.26674 ^a
313	30	0.97058	–	1.13165	–
318	30	0.96681	0.96681 ^a	0.99656	0.99656 ^a
323	30	0.96305	0.96305 ^a	0.86147	0.86147 ^a
298	40	0.96640	0.96640 ^a	1.73210	1.73210 ^a
303	40	0.96381	–	1.52760	–
308	40	0.96120	0.96120 ^a	1.32310	1.32310 ^a
313	40	0.95359	–	1.18412	–
318	40	0.94598	0.94598 ^a	1.04516	1.04516 ^a
323	40	0.93837	0.93837 ^a	0.90619	0.90619 ^a
298	60	0.94600	0.94601 ^a	1.49040	1.49042
303	60	0.94204	–	1.33984	–
308	60	0.93810	0.93810 ^a	1.18930	1.18931 ^a
313	60	0.93338	–	1.07421	–
318	60	0.92864	0.92863 ^a	0.95910	0.95909 ^a
323	60	0.92391	0.92391 ^a	0.84400	0.84400 ^a
298	80	0.91592	0.91592 ^a	0.92237	0.92371 ^a
303	80	0.91181	–	0.85386	–
308	80	0.90768	0.90768 ^a	0.78401	0.78400 ^a
313	80	0.90251	–	0.72270	–
318	80	0.89732	0.89732 ^a	0.66141	0.66140 ^a
323	80	0.89214	0.89214 ^a	0.60010	0.60010 ^a
298	100	0.88072	0.88072 ^a	0.46300	0.46300 ^a
			0.88070 ^b		0.46000 ^b
303	100	0.87595	–	0.44536	–
308	100	0.87116	0.87116 ^a	0.42770	0.42770 ^a
313	100	0.86627	–	0.40893	–
318	100	0.86140	0.86140 ^a	0.3917	0.3901 ^a
323	100	0.86051	0.86051 ^a	0.38921	0.38921 ^a

^aRefs. 5–7.^bRef. 18.

limiting apparent molar volume (V_ϕ^0) and experimental slope (S_v^*) were obtained by a computerized least-square method. Within experimental error, our values for V_ϕ^0 varied linearly with $\sqrt{c}$ to follow the equation¹⁰,

$$V_\phi = V_\phi^0 + S_v^* \sqrt{c} \quad (2)$$

where S_v^* is a constant dependent on charge and salt type and can be related to solute-solute interactions and V_ϕ^0 is the limiting apparent molar volume which is related to solute-

solvent interactions. The V_{ϕ}^0 values along with the experimental slopes (S_v^*) are listed in Table 2. The S_v^* values are positive and increase with increase of temperature

electrolytes and the positive increase in ϕ_E^0 with increasing temperature can be ascribed to the presence of caging or packing effect⁷.

Table 2. Limiting apparent molar volumes (V_{ϕ}^0) and experimental slopes (S_v^*) together with standard errors of different salts in 30 mass % tetrahydrofuran + water at different temperatures

Salt	V_{ϕ}^0 at various temp. ($\text{cm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$)					S_v^* at various temp. ($\text{dm}^{1/2} \text{mol}^{-3/2}$)				
	303	308	313	318	323 K	303	308	313	318	323 K
NH_4NO_3	44.07 (± 0.50)	26.88 (± 0.41)	15.64 (± 0.19)	11.26 (± 0.63)	2.79 (± 0.32)	32.22 (± 0.41)	42.09 (± 0.61)	51.48 (± 0.61)	55.84 (± 0.35)	59.04 (± 0.17)
KNO_3	11.06 (± 0.31)	9.57 (± 0.42)	6.35 (± 0.13)	0.61 (± 0.11)	0.06 (± 0.08)	62.89 (± 0.72)	63.60 (± 0.28)	64.11 (± 0.37)	65.26 (± 0.25)	66.08 (± 0.22)
$\text{Ca}(\text{NO}_3)_2$	90.04 (± 0.23)	70.557 (± 0.19)	54.25 (± 0.22)	45.34 (± 0.16)	18.59 (± 0.24)	115.67 (± 0.09)	120.85 (± 0.20)	126.68 (± 0.23)	139.58 (± 0.32)	159.10 (± 0.07)
$\text{Mg}(\text{NO}_3)_2$	108.21 (± 0.32)	70.95 (± 0.21)	59.84 (± 0.31)	51.21 (± 0.42)	46.44 (± 0.22)	114.82 (± 0.34)	140.00 (± 0.37)	157.34 (± 0.19)	166.93 (± 0.18)	172.42 (± 0.57)

for all examined salts suggesting that more and more solute is accommodated in the void space left in the packing of large associated solvent molecules. In order to examine the ion-solvent interactions, the V_{ϕ}^0 values can be used. Table 2 reveals that V_{ϕ}^0 values are positive and decrease with increasing temperature for all salts under investigation. This indicates that there is a large amount of electrostriction in these solutions which is higher at higher temperatures. Similar results are reported for some 1 : 1 electrolytes in aqueous DMF¹¹.

The variation of V_{ϕ}^0 with temperature of the electrolytes in this solvent mixture follows the polynomial equation,

$$V_{\phi}^0 = a_0 + a_1 T + a_2 T^2 \quad (3)$$

where T (K) is the temperature. The coefficients a_0 , a_1 and a_2 are determined and the following equations are obtained :

$$V_{\phi}^0 = 8303.25 - 50.89 T + 0.0780 T^2 \quad \text{for ammonium nitrate (4)}$$

$$V_{\phi}^0 = 369.23 - 0.97 T + 0.0008 T^2 \quad \text{for potassium nitrate (5)}$$

$$V_{\phi}^0 = 1232.10 - 3.95 T + 0.0006 T^2 \quad \text{for calcium nitrate (6)}$$

$$V_{\phi}^0 = 18170.87 - 112.64 T + 0.1550 T^2 \quad \text{for magnesium nitrate (7)}$$

The apparent molar expansibilities (ϕ_E^0) can be obtained by differentiating eq. (3) with respect to temperature,

$$\phi_E^0 = (\delta V_{\phi}^0 / \delta T)_p = a_1 + 2 a_2 T \quad (8)$$

The ϕ_E^0 values of the studied electrolytes at 303, 308, 313, 318 and 323 K are recorded in Table 3. It is evident that the ϕ_E^0 values increase with increasing temperature for all

Table 3. Limiting apparent molar expansibilities (ϕ_E^0) for various salts in 30 mass % tetrahydrofuran + water at different temperatures

Electrolytes	$\phi_E^0, \text{cm}^3 \text{mol}^{-3} \text{K}^{-1}$		
	303 K	313 K	323 K
NH_4NO_3	-3.62	-2.06	-0.50
KNO_3	-0.20	-0.15	-0.54
$\text{Ca}(\text{NO}_3)_2$	-3.58	-3.57	-3.56
$\text{Mg}(\text{NO}_3)_2$	-6.59	-3.09	-0.41

For determining structure-making /breaking capacities of solutes in different solvents and in different solvent-mixtures, following equation of Hepler¹³ was used,

$$(\delta \phi_E^0 / \delta T)_p = (\delta^2 V_{\phi}^0 / \delta T^2)_p \quad (9)$$

According to Hepler, structure-making solutes should have positive value and structure-breaking solutes negative value of the term of $(\delta^2 V_{\phi}^0 / \delta T^2)_p$ respectively. It has been observed that the values of $(\delta^2 V_{\phi}^0 / \delta T^2)_p$ for solutions of all electrolytes are positive, indicating the structure-making behaviour of these electrolytes, viz. NH_4NO_3 , KNO_3 , $\text{Mg}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ and $\text{Ca}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ in this solvent-mixture.

The viscosity data of solutions for various electrolytes, viz. NH_4NO_3 , KNO_3 , $\text{Mg}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ and $\text{Ca}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ in 30 mass % THF + H_2O mixture have been analyzed using Jones-Dole¹⁴ equation,

$$\eta / \eta_0 = 1 + A \sqrt{c} + Bc \quad (10)$$

$$(\eta / \eta_0 - 1) / \sqrt{c} = A + Bc$$

$$\text{where, } \eta = (Kt - L/t) \rho$$

where η_0 and η are the viscosities of solvent-mixture and solution, respectively, A and B are constants, ρ is the density of the solvent-mixture and K and L are constants for a

particular viscometer. The values of *A* and *B* are estimated by computerized least squares method and recorded in Table 4. The results show that the values of *B*-coefficient for all studied electrolytes are positive and these values decrease with increasing temperature. This indicates that these electrolytes NH₄NO₃, KNO₃, Mg(NO₃)₂, Ca(NO₃)₂ act as structure-maker in this solvent-mixture. A similar result was reported by other workers¹⁵ in the case of viscosities of perchlorate of lithium and sodium in propionic acid + ethanol mixture.

It has been reported by a number of workers that *dB/dT* is a better criterion¹⁶ for determining the structure-making/breaking nature of any electrolyte rather than simply the *B*-coefficient. It is evident from Table 4 that the values of *B* are positive and decrease with rise in temperature (negative *dB/dT*), suggesting structure-making tendencies of all electrolytes in this mixed solvent system. These conclusions

It is seen from Table 5 that all the salts studied here have negative limiting apparent molal adiabatic compressibilities, ϕ_k^0 which become more negative with increasing temperature. Negative ϕ_k^0 values of the salts are interpreted in terms of the loss of compressibility of THF + water mixture due to electrostrictive forces in the vicinity of the ions. On rising the temperature of the system, the metal ions lose some solvent molecules from their first coordination sphere in a process which is expected to increase the compressibility. But at higher temperature, breakdown of the intermolecular hydrogen bonds in the THF + water mixed system also takes place more effectively resulting in a loss of compressibility. Thus it may be concluded that for the studied salts solutions, the latter effect is growing faster and overriding the former as far as the present temperature range is concerned. From Table 5 it is also evident that limiting experimental slopes (*S_k^{*}*) have positive values indicating the existence of strong

Table 4. Values of *B* (cm³ mol⁻¹) and *A* (cm^{3/2} mol^{-1/2}) parameters together with standard errors for ammonium nitrate, sodium potassium nitrate, calcium nitrate and magnesium nitrate in 30 mass % THF + H₂O mixture at different temperature*

Electrolyte	<i>A</i> values of different temp.					<i>B</i> values of different temp.				
	303	308	313	318	323 K	303	308	313	318	323 K
NH ₄ NO ₃	-1.92 (±0.08)	-1.58 (±0.11)	-1.51 (±0.17)	-1.42 (±0.27)	-1.34 (±0.21)	2.97 (±0.37)	2.26 (±0.78)	2.01 (±0.06)	1.91 (±0.26)	1.86 (±0.01)
KNO ₃	-1.70 (±0.23)	-1.67 (±0.31)	-1.66 (±0.19)	-1.59 (±0.18)	-1.46 (±0.02)	2.46 (±0.11)	2.32 (±0.05)	2.31 (±0.25)	2.18 (±0.11)	2.04 (±0.09)
Ca(NO ₃) ₂	-1.60 (±0.01)	-1.58 (±0.11)	-1.55 (±0.72)	-1.45 (±0.18)	-1.32 (±0.04)	2.41 (±0.19)	2.39 (±0.22)	2.30 (±0.21)	2.19 (±0.01)	2.06 (±0.11)
Mg(NO ₃) ₂	-1.61 (±0.13)	-1.46 (±0.21)	-1.33 (±0.11)	-1.27 (±0.19)	-1.13 (±1.08)	2.39 (±0.21)	2.19 (±0.10)	1.66 (±0.19)	1.63 (±0.09)	1.62 ^a (±0.21)

*Values in parenthesis are standard errors.

are in excellent agreement with that drawn from $(\delta^2 V_\phi^0 / \delta T^2)_p$ obtained earlier.

Adiabatic compressibility coefficients (*β*) were derived from the relation,

$$\beta = 1/\mu^2 \rho \tag{11}$$

where ρ is the solution density and u the sound velocity in the solution. The apparent molal adiabatic compressibility (ϕ_k^0) of the liquid solutions was calculated from the relation,

$$\phi_k = M/\rho_0 + 1000(\beta \rho_0 - \beta_0 \rho)m \rho \rho_0 \tag{12}$$

The limiting apparent molal adiabatic compressibilities (ϕ_k^0) were obtained by extrapolating the plots of ϕ_k versus the square-root of molal concentration of the solute to zero concentration by the computerized least-squares method,

$$\phi_k = \phi_k^0 + S_k^* m^{1/2} \tag{13}$$

The values of ϕ_k^0 and *S_k^{*}* are reported in Table 5.

Table 5. Limiting apparent molal adiabatic compressibility, ϕ_k^0 (m³mol⁻¹Pa⁻¹) and experimental slope, *S_k^{*}* (m³ mol^{-3/2} Pa⁻¹ kg^{1/2}) of some metal nitrates in 30 mass % THF + water mixture at various temperatures*

Salt	$\phi_k^0 \times 10^4$ (m ³ mol ⁻¹ Pa ⁻¹)			<i>S_k[*]</i> × 10 ⁴ (m ³ mol ^{-3/2} Pa ⁻¹ kg ^{1/2})		
	303	313	323 K	303	313	323 K
NH ₄ NO ₃	-0.77 (±0.07)	-2.67 (±0.01)	-3.44 (±0.08)	0.82 (±0.10)	4.48 (±0.06)	5.55 (±0.01)
KNO ₃	-1.88 (±0.03)	-2.23 (±0.09)	-3.59 (±0.02)	2.89 (±0.01)	3.33 (±0.05)	5.41 (±0.09)
Ca(NO ₃) ₂	-1.35 (±0.01)	-2.27 (±0.11)	-3.09 (±0.04)	2.12 (±0.09)	3.34 (±0.02)	3.37 (±0.01)
Mg(NO ₃) ₂	-0.36 (±0.03)	-3.53 (±0.01)	-6.78 (±1.08)	0.29 (±0.10)	6.41 (±0.09)	11.81 (±0.03)

*Values in parenthesis are standard errors.

solute-solute interactions in the studied solvent system which resembles the agreement drawn from S_{C}^* discussed earlier. A similar result was reported by us¹⁷ in the case of ultrasonic studies of some alkali metal chlorides and bromides in THF + water mixture.

Experimental

Tetrahydrofuran (THF; Merck) was kept for several days over KOH, refluxed for 24 h and distilled over LiAlH_4 as described earlier⁶. The purified solvent had a boiling point of 66°, a density of 0.88072 g cm³, a coefficient of viscosity of 0.00460 p and a specific conductance of ca. 0.81×10^{-6} S cm⁻¹ at 25°. These values are in good agreement with the literature data¹⁸.

Ammonium nitrate, potassium nitrate, magnesium nitrate and calcium nitrate (A.R., Sd. Fine chemicals) were used as such, only after drying over P_2O_5 in a desiccator for more than 48 h. Freshly distilled conductivity water was used. The binary aqueous solutions of tetrahydrofuran as well as the solutions of nitrates were made by weight and conversion of molality into molarity was done¹⁹.

Density was measured with an Ostwald-Sprengel type pycnometer having a bulb volume of 25 cm³ and an internal diameter of the capillary of about 0.1 cm. The pycnometer was calibrated at 25, 35 and 45° with double-distilled water and benzene. The pycnometer with the test solution was equilibrated in a water-bath maintained at $\pm 0.01^\circ$ of the desired temperature by means of a mercury in glass thermoregulator and the temperature was determined by a calibrated thermometer and Muller bridge. The pycnometer was then removed from the thermostatic bath, properly dried and weighted. The evaporation losses remained insignificant during the time of actual measurements. An average of triplicate measurements was taken into account. The density values are reproducible to $\pm 3 \times 10^{-5}$ g cm⁻³. Details have been described earlier⁶. Viscosity was measured by means of suspended-level Ubbelohde²⁰ viscometer at the desired temperature (accuracy $\pm 0.01^\circ$). The precision of the viscosity measurements was 0.05%. Details have been described earlier⁶. Sound velocity was determined with an accuracy of 0.3% using a single crystal variable-path ultrasonic interferometer (Mittal Enterprises, India) working at 4 MHz, which was calibrated with water, methanol and benzene at each temperature. The temperature stability was maintained within ± 0.01 K by circulating thermostated water around the cell by a circulating pump.

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